

SOCIAL SCIENCES

POVERTY AS A PROBLEM AND DEVELOPMENT FACTOR IN SOCIETY

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Abstract

Many social problems have always acted and continue to act not only as a factor that creates difficulties and harms society, but also as an aspect that stimulates the development of that society. Responding in a timely manner and adapting to perfection has been a factor in human evolution throughout history. Today, there are problems and issues of any form and scale, the solution of which is important and necessary. However, some issues can never be fully resolved, the human factor, the interests of individuals, and so on. does not allow it. Therefore, in reality, we should see problems only in an adaptive form in terms of incentives for development. The word "problem" should not be seen as a negative concept, but as a factor leading to a better and more developed environment. The fact that human history has come to its present state after such a long time is due to the fact that there are many "problems" and human initiatives. One issue that needs to be addressed is the foundation of a new future.

Keywords: Social problem, problem and issue, development, stimulus, improvement, society, interests.

Problems have always existed as factors that are relevant and concern people. From another point of view, the concept of "problem" is not only as a negative phenomenon, but as a sign guiding towards development. Considering poverty, we can see that it is a matter that exists at any time and is constantly being fought. Poverty has been and has been a natural process, leading to many complications both economically and socially. With the formation of society, the process of resource allocation arose in parallel, which is the most important aspect in the emergence of inequality. The diversity of human categories leads to the fact that in the society in which they live, resources are divided according to those categories. Given that the political situation in different parts of the world is different, it is possible to determine the difference of poverty. In the society in which we live, each process is realized, resolved on the basis of political issues, etc. Political relations differ in individual countries, including in poverty [3].

The most important point in considering poverty as a "issue" rather than a "problem" is that in any case, this issue remains real and relevant, and it exists as a starting point for further development. If humanity accelerates the evolutionary process on the way to eradicating poverty and has been doing it for millennia, then this natural process is the basis of new beginnings, having the character of an incentive.

The problem of poverty has worried human society since ancient times. However, despite this, humanity has not been able to solve this problem. And paradoxically, poverty continues to be an integral feature of any society. The fight against poverty and inequality is one of the main tasks of the socio-economic policy of any state. To date, there is no single methodology for solving this problem, since each work requires an individual innovative approach. Unequal access of members of society to any necessary resources, both material and intangible, is called social inequality [5].

Poverty is a "pronounced decrease in well-being", that is, the economic situation in which a person or group of persons cannot meet a certain minimum of

needs necessary for the preservation and improvement of life, working capacity. Poverty is a relative and ambiguous concept and depends on the general standard of living in a particular society (Gini coefficient, Theil index). The poor are a vulnerable stratum of society, and this, in a sense, slows down the development of the country. In other words, they are those who do not have enough funds or whose level of consumption is insufficient to keep them above a certain level of poverty. These people may not have a home, food, or a decent state of Health, which leads to a change in the level of nutrition or literacy. Poverty can always be compared to a depth without a bottom that pulls down [8].

Poverty is not a catastrophic factor, but this deficiency hinders the development of both developing and developing countries. Therefore, the great powers of the present world are fighting precisely against poverty and inequality. But what about underdeveloped and developing countries? Because it is impossible to achieve any development and progress without reducing the level of poverty in the country.

Poverty is the result of various and interrelated causes and is grouped in the following aspects: [4]

- * Economic (unemployment, economic inequality, including low wages, low labor productivity, competitiveness of the industry);

- * Socio-medical (disability, old age, morbidity);

- * Demographic (single-parent families, a large number of dependents in the family, overpopulation);

- * Educational specialization (low level of education, lack of sufficient professional training);

- * Political (military conflicts, forced migration), etc.

Thus, understanding poverty, it can be conditionally divided into 3 subspecies: absolute, relative, income-based or multidimensional, which is called a numerical measurement of poverty. For example, in 2012, the US government set the poverty line for a family of 4 at \$ 23,050 per year. But, despite this, many people remained outside this line. Thus, it can be concluded that if the state has a certain limit or limit in poverty, it

does not insure either the state or the vulnerable segment of the population against poverty.

Absolute poverty means the absence or partial satisfaction of basic needs (food, clothing and housing). British scientists Charles Booth and Seab Rowntree, who introduced the concept of the poverty line, began to engage in quantitative calculations of the poverty level in the 1890s.

The poverty line is only the minimum income required to obtain the necessary food, clothing and shelter. If the state sets the poverty line, then it is nominal, and the real one is very different. And people who remain on the other side of the poverty line are in a state of "chronic poverty." [7]

Relative poverty refers to the poverty of a person compared to other people in a given society. This is the difference between absolute and relative poverty. That is, the first group includes the necessary goods and services, and the second includes people who are provided with vital things and services, but cannot maintain the "standard" accepted in society.

The UN applies the term "Least Developed Countries" to poor areas, as many respondents are embarrassed to admit that they are poor. According to UN data for 2019, the list of "Least Developed Countries" includes 47 countries, including Tajikistan, Afghanistan, Moldova and Ukraine. This status is granted according to three criteria: [2]

- * State economic weakness index;

- * The level of income of the population or GDP per capita over the past three years;

- * Real quality of life assessment.

The index of economic weakness or the index of State weakness (index of Failed States) is a complex indicator that characterizes the ability (incapacity) of the authorities of a country to control the integrity of its territory, as well as the demographic, political and economic situation.

Assessment of real quality of life or index of quality of life - correlates the results of studies on the subjective assessment of life in countries with objective determinants of the quality of life in these countries [7]. The Human Development Index was calculated in 2013 (from the Economic Intelligence Unit) and covers 80 countries, with Switzerland, Australia and Norway leading.

The cost of living is a very important indicator. On its basis, the minimum wage, the amount of pensions and benefits are determined, Republican and regional budgets are calculated, social programs are developed [9].

It is one of the important issues to differentiate and evaluate the processes and situations taking place in society in various forms and aspects. Many times, when assessing the situation taking place, the process of thought formation is formed according to the established criteria. Considering that there are categories of different groups of society, the aspect of thinking can change and form based on this. Any event from its form and structure leads to processes such as development

and improvement. From a certain point of view, situations such as difficulties and problems have supported the formation of a better and more complex society and life throughout human history. Just as each person forms a personal opinion and opinion against a particular process or object, as well as the issue of poverty is no exception. Poverty is one of the issues that has been relevant, formed, developed and changed with us, almost from the moment of human existence to the present day, which has caused many deaths over many years [6].

Based on Maslov's theory of needs, we can see that physical demand is a matter that is located higher than all other needs and is one of the important aspects. It is on these characteristics that all the processes taking place in human life take place. Considering that not every event and process exists spontaneously, and each has a reason for its occurrence. Various interdependent phenomena affect in a systematic form, creating more diverse factors. The issue of poverty refers to the processes and phenomena inherent in human society. Because the emergence of understanding is intended for the surplus of the current socio-economic situation within society and is intended to explain this aspect.

An unambiguous answer to the question of whether poverty is a problem or a matter cannot be found, and it is not correct. It acts as a process that changes in terms of context depending on which side we look at it from. In the philosophical sense, poverty is a state that is an integral part of society, always stimulating development by its existence. In the socio-economic sense, poverty is a situation that causes many problems in society and the country, which must be resolved, completely or partially eliminated. Both thoughts can be considered correct, the relevance of each is a fact [1].

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